
THE INSTITUTE OF ENGINEERS OF IRELAND, GEOTECHNICAL SOCIETY

**MEASUREMENT AND ANALYSIS OF ROCK MASS
FRACTURES AND THEIR APPLICATIONS IN CIVIL
ENGINEERING**

PAUL QUIGLEY, B Eng (Hons), MIEI, FGS
Geotechnical Engineer, IGSL Limited

STEVEN McSWINEY, B Mod Geol, MSc
Engineering Geologist, IGSL Limited

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SYNOPSIS

This paper reviews current practices for measuring fracture spacings and determining the excavability of rock masses. A new method for measuring, presenting and analysing the fracture state of a rock mass is presented. The fracture data obtained from this approach can then be analysed and used to predict the excavability characteristics of a rock mass.

1. INTRODUCTION

The evaluation of rock mass excavation (i.e. its excavability) has become an increasingly important factor in the economics of civil engineering, particularly for road and motorway construction projects. The most common problem associated with rock excavation is the incorrect assessment of its fracture state. This can result in large delays to the programme with consequent claims and tends to reflect poorly on the service provided by the geotechnical professional.

In many instances the inadequacy of the geotechnical data is due to cost-cutting in the investigation programme. Where rock excavation is required in civil engineering schemes, it is extremely important that the engineer designs and specifies the geotechnical investigations such as to provide the necessary information on the intrinsic characteristics of the rock mass.

It is generally accepted that it is cheaper to excavate rock masses by ripping than by drill and blast, however productivity may be lower. If the ripped blocks are too large to be fed into a crusher then the additional breaking required may make the ripping both impractical and uneconomic.

The recent increase in the number of Clause 12 claims (“unforeseen ground conditions”) arising from unsuccessful rock excavation using mechanical methods has led to much controversy and dispute between civil engineering contractors and client engineers. These problems are

generally caused either by contractors incorrectly evaluating the geotechnical data provided or the data presented being unrepresentative of the “as-found” conditions.

Many engineers and geologists take a very simplistic view of core log mechanical indices, particularly rock quality designation values (RQD) and tend to over rely on RQD values as a means of determining the quality and degree of intactness of a rock mass. The authors have experience of cases where an overall mean value of the RQD’s is simply taken and used to predict the anticipated method of excavation!

There is a natural tendency to assume that high RQD values reflect stronger and more competent rock. In other cases, characteristic RQD values have been used to determine stand-up times and support requirements for underground excavations. We believe that this simplistic approach stems from a lack of understanding of the parameters which govern the excavability of rock masses or that they are considered to be too complex and cannot be relied upon to predict excavation methods or in-situ behaviour.

In addition to road cut and trench excavations, the authors’ method of measuring and analysing fracture spacings has many applications in civil engineering schemes which benefit from good quality fracture spacing data.

These include:

- *shafts and tunnels*
- *rockfill, rock armour and rip-rap*
- *piles socketed into bedrock*
- *slope stability*
- *hydrogeological modelling*

This paper firstly reviews current methods and procedures for measuring fracture spacing data and outlines current excavability assessment systems. The applications of the authors' method for measuring and analysing fracture spacing data are presented in the form of two case histories. It is hoped that this paper will assist engineers and geologists in their understanding of the parameters which control or govern rock mass excavation.

2. MECHANICAL INDICIES, FRACTURE LOGGING AND ROCK STRENGTH

2.1 General

As outlined previously, one of the common problems associated with rock excavation during civil engineering works is the incorrect assessment of the fracture state of the rock mass. The mechanical indices and fracture spacings are probably the most important part of a core log record and provide vital detail on the engineering characteristics of the rock mass.

Given that core recoveries may be poor in weak, unconsolidated or disturbed rock masses, then the correct interpretation of the rock core (by the engineering geologist

or the geotechnical engineer) and its representation in terms of the in-situ condition is even more important.

2.2 Mechanical Indices

The need for measuring and representing the degree of intactness of a rockmass was recognised in the early 1960's. Deere and his co-workers introduced RQD and traditionally three standard methods have been performed on each core run:

- *total core recovery (TCR)*
- *solid core recovery (SCR)*
- *rock quality designation (RQD)*

BS 5930 (Code of Practice for Site Investigation) provides definitions for each of the aforementioned indices. In summary, the TCR is the total length of the core recovered expressed as a percentage of the core run length. Similarly, SCR is the cumulative length of pieces of solid core recovered and is also expressed as percentage of the core run length. RQD is defined as the cumulative length of solid core pieces greater than 100mm in length and again is expressed as a percentage of the core run length.

An important aspect inherent in the definition of SCR and RQD, and one which is not often appreciated, is the definition of solid core. BS 5930 defines solid core as 'solid cylinders (of core)'. However, for the purposes of measuring RQD, solid core is defined as 'sound lengths (presumably core pieces containing solid core) which are 100mm or more in length'. Elsewhere it is stated that the measurement of RQD

should be made along the core axis, this is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1

Solid Core/RQD as defined by BS 5930

In this respect, BS 5930 has failed to provide clear and workable definitions of the mechanical indices, particularly fracture spacing or fracture frequency, which in fact has been omitted. Given that solid core is defined as intact cylinders of rock while RQD is defined as being measured along the core axis, this can lead to situations where the RQD actually exceeds the solid core recovery!

The rigid application of these definitions to measurements made on core can be extremely misleading for the following reasons. Neither of the above definitions takes into account the effect of the orientation of discontinuities and drilling direction. For example, a vertical hole drilled through a rockmass with a

horizontal bedding would be expected to produce 100% SCR. If the spacing of the bedding was say 120mm a RQD of 100% may also result.

If we take the same rockmass and rotate it through 70° and examine the SCR and RQD measurements from a vertical drillhole, a very significant drop in the values of SCR and RQD would be obtained. This model, however simplistic, illustrates a fundamental flaw in BS 5930's definition of SCR and RQD.

It is readily apparent that the values of SCR and RQD, as defined by BS 5930, are not only dependant on the degree of fracturing present in the rockmass but also on the relative orientation of drilling to the dominant joint sets. This is clearly unsatisfactory if such parameters are to be carried through to excavatability analysis, tunnel rock mass rating and rock armour evaluation.

In order to overcome the anomaly with orientation effectively, the authors recommend that solid core is measured in accordance with Norbury's definition where solid core is defined as 'core with at least one full diameter but not necessarily a full circumference'. This definition removes the ambiguity of including steep discontinuities in the core measurements and gives higher percentages of solid core as compared to BS 5930. Using Norbury's definition, core with an inclined set of discontinuities can have solid core of 100%, this is illustrated in Figures 2 and 3.

Figure 2
Solid Core as defined by Norbury

As RQD is usually calculated for each core run, the RQD value measured does not take into account any changes of fracture state within the core run. Changes in lithology (rock type) are often associated with variable fracture patterns owing to the different mechanical properties of each rock type.

Consider a sequence of interbedded calcareous mudstones and calcisiltite limestones. The limestone unit may dominate in contributing to the RQD values. The RQD's measured will overestimate the fracture state of the limestone units and underestimate the degree of fracturing in the less competent mudstone horizons.

Figure 3
Schematic Illustration of Core Measurements and Fracture Indices

Hawkins (1986) recommended that this particular problem could be avoided if the RQD values related to the lithological units rather than core run length. A lithological quality index (LQD) could be shown adjacent to the RQD column on the core log record. In addition to this, Hawkins suggested that an RQD₃₀₀ should be introduced. This would be calculated from core lengths exceeding 300mm. His reasoning behind this proposal was that 300mm approximated to the maximum block thickness that could be ripped.

An example of the relationship between RQD and LQD on two adjacent core runs is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4
LQD/RQD after Hawkins

Description and Classification of Soils and Rocks		
RQD values	mm	LQD values
RQD ₁₀₀ =55%	90 90 90 90 90	LQD ₁₀₀ =0% LQD ₃₀₀ =0%
RQD ₃₀₀ =55%	550	LQD ₁₀₀ =100% LQD ₃₀₀ =100%
Drilling break	Limestone	
RQD ₁₀₀ =55%	550mm	
RQD ₃₀₀ =55%	90 90 90 90 90	LQD ₁₀₀ =0% LQD ₃₀₀ =0%
RQD: Rock Quality Designation LQD: Lithological Quality Designation		
Relationship of RQD and LQD on two adjacent core runs (after Hawkins 1986)		

Deere introduced descriptive terms which relate to RQD values and which have been incorporated into BS 5930. These are shown in Table 1. This classification is considered to be highly ambiguous as the terms are dependent on the application in question, i.e. rock excavation, tunnelling, slope stability, rock armour or piling.

Table 1 - Descriptive terms relating to RQD(as per BS 5930)

RQD (%)	Term
0 to 25	Very poor
25 to 50	Poor
50 to 75	Fair
75 to 90	Good
90 to 100	Excellent

2.3 Fracture Spacing

Two other terms denoting the spacing of fractures or discontinuities are commonly presented on core log records: fracture spacing (If) and fracture index (Fi). The former is defined as the average length of solid core pieces over lengths of core of uniform lithology (not necessarily core runs). Minimum, average and maximum fracture spacings can also be measured and recorded on the core log records.

Fracture index (Fi) is defined as the number of fractures per metre. It is emphasised that the fracture spacing must be related to lithology and not core run length, in order to have any real meaning. The term 'non-intact' is used for highly fractured or fragmented core where the

rock material is usually recovered as fine to coarse gravel size angular fragments.

Fi and If values have been related to RQD by various formulae, the most notable of these being that proposed by Priest and Hudson (1987) who presented the following relationship:

$$RQD = 100e^{-0.1\hat{r}}(0.1\hat{r} + 1)$$

Where \hat{r} is the number of fractures per metre or Fi. This is illustrated in Figure 5.

In general some scatter is usually measured on any such data and while a relatively good correlation between the number of fractures per metre and RQD may be apparent, it is revealing to convert the Fi data into real spacings (If data) and re-plot the comparison. This has been carried out and Figures 6 and 7 show that (even for a single lithology) the

relationship is highly unreliable for RQD values in excess of 50%.

It is the opinion of the authors that RQD values greater than 50% should not be used to deduce or interpolate fracture spacings.

When the mechanical indices were first introduced it was impractical to represent each fracture intersected during drilling (considering that 200 fractures for 10mm drilled would not be unusual) on core log records. With the advent of affordable personal computers and user-friendly software packages it is now feasible to record and present graphically each fracture on the core log record.

Figure 5 Relationship between RQD and Fracture Frequency after Priest and Hudson

In turn, the recording of this data permits detailed analysis of the fracture spacings (i.e. frequency analysis). This aspect is discussed in Section 3. It is also now

possible and practical to work directly with "real" fracture spacing data as opposed to the commonly used mechanical indices.

Figure 6 Illustration of Relationship between RQD and Fracture Frequency after Deere

Figure 7 Illustration of Transformation of RQD to Fracture Spacing

2.4 Effects of Discontinuities and Drilling Orientation on Fracture Spacing.

The principal aim of measuring fracture indices (F_i , I_f) and indeed the method outlined in the paper is to establish an accurate representation of the discontinuity spacings throughout a rock mass. Generally speaking, a rock mass will contain at least three systematic joint

sets (usually but not always approximately orthogonal to each other).

Non-systematic joints are also likely to be present. Each of the systematic joint sets will possess a distribution of fracture spacings. Examples of typical discontinuity patterns within a rock mass structure are illustrated in Figure 8.

Figure 8 Illustration of Discontinuity Patterns for Typical Rock Mass Structures

A. Blocky

[approximately equidimensional – largest dimension not greater than twice the smallest]

B. Tabular

[smallest dimension greater than 60mm; other dimensions at least twice the smallest]

C. Flaggy

[smallest dimension 20-60mm; other dimensions at least twice the smallest]

D. Slaty or Shaly

[smallest dimension less than 20mm; other dimensions at least twice the smallest]

E. Irregular

[including pyramidal]

F. Columnar or Elongated

[largest dimension at least twice each of the others]

Descriptions such as “blocky – tabular” may be used where block shapes are borderline

If we consider a model rock mass containing three orthogonal joint sets inclined from the horizontal (typically the case within the Dublin Basin Limestones) and each with the same joint spacing (J_s),

then take a hypothetical drillhole intersecting the rockmass, the average fracture spacing measured from the hole may be significantly less than J_s . This is despite the apparent spacing for dipping

joint sets being greater than the true spacing!

This effect is due to the fact that the recognised methods do not distinguish between joints belonging to different sets but simply take measurements between succeeding fractures as encountered in the core. This is distinct from making measurements between succeeding joints with the same orientation (i.e. belonging to the same joint set). By failing to discriminate between joint sets the measurements will generate an artificial distribution of fractures.

In order to deduce realistic joint spacing values, allowance must be made for the relative orientation of drilling to joint surfaces and for the artificially generated distribution which will be generated if individual systematic joint sets are not distinguished.

The influence of discontinuity dip on apparent fracture spacing is shown in Figure 9. Also illustrated is how an artificial distribution can be generated if discontinuity sets are not distinguished.

2.5 Rock Strength

Rock strength is usually defined in terms of unconfined compressive strength (UCS) and has an approximate linear relationship with point load strength. Some workers have found that point load values lower than 2.0MPa can be unreliable. However, Pettifer and Fookes found test results as low as 0.5MPa to be reliable and consistent. This endorsed the findings of

Hawkins (1986) who recommended that point load values of less than 0.5MPa should not be used.

Figure 9 Influence of dip of joints on apparent fracture spacing.

A conversion factor of between 18 and 24 is normally used to correlate UCS and Is_{50} . The authors generally use a factor of 20 and have found this to give a good correlation for the Dublin Basin Carboniferous limestones ("Calp"). For large projects or remote geological formations, it is advised that a specific correlation factor is derived.

Given the importance of rock strength, the authors strongly recommend that representative point load indices should be determined for each lithological unit encountered within a core log record. An example of how point load strength data can be presented in this manner is illustrated in Figure 11 (Section 3.0).

3.0 AUTHORS' GRAPHIC FRACTURE LOG AND DATA MANIPULATION

The authors have developed an engineering geological core log record on which a graphical representation of the fracture state of the rock mass is presented. This is in addition to the three standard mechanical indices (TCR, SCR and RQD). The mechanical indices are measured in accordance with Norbury et al. The data from which the fracture spacing log is compiled is maintained in digital form on the core log spreadsheet. The data on the fracture state of the rock mass can be then manipulated to produce interpretations of the true fracture spacings.

The recording of the fracture spacing is carried out during logging of the core. The down hole depth of each fracture is recorded. In addition to this, each fracture

is assigned to a joint set and the dip of the fracture recorded. An example of a data record sheet is presented in Figure 10.

The fracture logging works best where total core recovery is high (i.e. 80 to 100%) and where the core is intact. In such cases a high degree of confidence in the depths measured can be assumed.

Procedures for representing core loss and non-intact core have also been developed. Where significant core loss has occurred, the core is closely inspected to identify the core loss zone. Washing out of highly weathered zones and drilling through solution weathered cavities are examples of mechanisms by which core loss can occur.

Figure 10 Fracture Data Record Sheet

Fracture Logging Data Record Sheet				Drillhole No. 101			
Fracture Depth (m)	Dip (°)	Joint Set	Remarks (Lithology, strength, weathering)	Fracture Depth (m)	Dip (°)	Joint Set	Remarks (Lithology, strength, weathering)
2.5	SH	J1	AL, MW, Weak	3.14	SH	J1	AL, MW, Mod.Weak
2.53	SH	J1	"	3.22	SH	J1	"
2.55	70	J2	CL, SW, MS to S	3.24	SH	J1	"
2.59	70	J2		3.29	70	J2	CL, SW, S and VS
NI to 2.74				3.41	SH	J1	AL, MW, Mod.strong
2.8	SH	J1	AL, MW, Weak	3.65	SH	J1	"
2.95	SV	J3	CL, SW, S	3.72	70	J2	CL, SW, S
3.01	70	J2	CL, SW, S to VS				

Where non-intact core is recovered the natural fracture spacing is usually extremely closely spaced (i.e. < 20mm). For the purposes of generating the graphic fracture log, the fracture spacing for a non-intact zone is inferred by inspection of the returned fragments and the amount of core loss which has occurred within the non-intact zone. The only reference points in the recovered core are the drilling breaks at the end of each core run.

Once the data has been recorded it is entered into the spreadsheet template which calculates the fracture spacings between succeeding fractures. Where non-intact zones are intersected a fracture spacing value is attributed to the zone based on visual inspection of the core.

The fracture spacings are plotted to scale on the core log record as a fracture spacing versus depth plot. An example of a geotechnical core log record with the graphic fracture spacing log is presented in Figure 11.

A frequency analysis of the fracture spacings can then be carried out on each drillhole or for combined fracture data from several drillholes. To interpret the frequency analysis the cumulative length of core for each fracture spacing must be calculated and expressed as a percentage of the length drilled.

Take an example where 100m of rock is cored and say 150 occurrences of fracture spacings of 20mm recorded, then the cumulative length of core for this fracture

spacing would be 3m, i.e. 3% of the rock mass. Similarly, 80 occurrences of 200mm fracture spacing would represent 16% of the rock mass drilled.

Once these percentages are calculated for each fracture spacing, a histogram of percentage rock mass against fracture spacing categories can be produced. An example of a typical fracture spacing histogram is presented in Figures 13 and 14 (Section 5.1.3).

As outlined earlier, the distribution of frequencies will have a component which is artificially generated if joints sets are not distinguished. This is superimposed on the natural distribution generated by fracture spacings of each systematic joint set.

This effect can be overcome by two methods. Firstly, the above analysis can be carried out on joints belonging to a single systematic joint set (e.g. bedding). Similar analysis can also be carried out for each of the other systematic joint sets intercepted. Allowance can then be made for the angle between the joint set and orientation of drilling in the calculation of true fracture spacings for each set.

This method of analysis works reasonably well for joint sets where the inter-angle between drilling and joint orientation is high. Thus, depending on the orientation of drilling, one or possibly two joint sets will be well represented. In order to analyse other joint sets it may be necessary to alter the orientation of drilling

(i.e. drill an angled hole at the same location).

Figure 11 Example of Geotechnical Core Log Record with Graphic Fracture Log

Economics may dictate that only vertical holes can be drilled. In this case an alternative method can be employed to

correct for artificial distributions caused by orientation effects. This method requires

inspection of the cores to identify principle joint set orientations.

A computer model can be generated with these orientations using selected joint spacings and a frequency analysis performed on the modelled data. The shift away from the known selected fracture spacing can then be determined and the real data measured from the core adjusted accordingly. The distribution remaining after this adjustment has been made is attributed to the natural distribution of the true fracture spacings.

4.0 REVIEW OF EXCAVATIBILITY ASSESSMENT METHODS

In principal, the excavatibility of a rock mass depends on the geotechnical properties of the rock, the type and size of equipment to be used and the method of working. The dominant geotechnical factors which affect excavatibility/rippability and hence productivity are:

- *uniaxial compressive strength of the rock*
- *degree of weathering and integrity of the rock fabric*
- *spacing, orientation & persistence of bedding and discontinuities*
- *aperture, infilling and roughness of discontinuities.*

In addition to the above, consideration must also be given to access to the working area for different types of excavation plant.

The two most important geotechnical factors are considered to be the

discontinuity (or fracture) spacing and the intact strength of the rock. The orientation and aperture (or separation) of the discontinuities are also important criteria in that they determine whether the excavator bucket or ripper shank (tine) can penetrate and displace the individual blocks.

A number of methods have been developed for assessing rocks mass excavatibility. The most notable of these are:

- Franklin, Broch & Walton (1971)
- Weaver (1975)
- Kirsten (1982)
- Scoble & Muftuoglu (1984)
- Pettifer & Fookes (1994)

Franklin and his co-workers carried out the earliest work on rippability where rock strength and discontinuity spacing in relation to the method of excavation was presented graphically. The graph was divided into zones to delineate whether digging, ripping, blast to loosen or blast to fragment was required to excavate a rock mass. This method was based on case history performance between 1968 and 1970 and proved to be very useful and popular for rapid assessments. An example of the Franklin Chart is shown in Figure 12.

Weaver developed a rippability-rating chart which was derived from Bieniawski's Rock Mass Rating (RMR) system for tunnel support in South Africa. This assessment provides a rating of the rock mass ranging from 0 to 100. The parameters used to generate the rating

comprise rock strength, weathering, discontinuity spacing, persistence, infill, dip and dip direction.

Figure 12 Franklin Chart

Kirsten also based his assessment on South African case histories and used the NGI system to develop an excavability index 'N'. Weaver replaced RQD's with seismic velocities and introduced a weathering parameter and adjustments for discontinuity orientation. Kirsten's index excluded seismic velocity but incorporated RQD values.

Scoble & Muftuoglu developed a diggability index, based on UK opencast coal mines. This index mainly relies on the rock strength, discontinuity spacing and degree of weathering. Seismic velocity and weathering were retained but they introduced a parameter for abrasiveness. Rock strength was expressed in terms of tensile strength and discontinuity aperture and infill was incorporated in the weathering parameter.

Pettifer & Fookes have reviewed and updated the original Franklin chart. This is

based on their collection of over one hundred case histories (UK, Africa and Hong Kong) and is correlated with the performance of the latest generation of hydraulic excavators and dozers. Their revised graph is based on rock strength and mean discontinuity spacings which, as discussed previously, are considered to be the two critical geotechnical parameters governing excavability.

Pettifer & Fookes highlight that whenever possible a three-dimensional discontinuity spacing index should be used, as this will provide a more realistic assessment of the average block size. This is taken as the average of the characteristic fracture spacings of the systematic joint sets present in the rock mass. They recommend that the point load index test is used for the purpose of determining strength and that discontinuity spacing data should, if at all possible, be obtained from both outcrops and rock cores.

In addition to these rating systems, plant manufacturers such as Caterpillar and Komatsu have produced performance handbooks on ripping. These correlate dozer size with seismic velocities for various rock types. The seismic velocity of the rock is compared with ripper performance in a variety of rock types.

Kirsten (1982) argued that seismic velocity could only provide a provisional indication of the excavability characteristics of a rock mass, pointing out that in terms of overall assessment seismic velocity cannot be determined to an accuracy

better than 20%. Furthermore, seismic velocity may vary by as much as 1,000 m/s in apparently identical formations. Karpuz and Bozdog (1990) have noted that these charts tend to over-estimate the ease of ripping.

The development of larger and more powerful dozers has significantly increased ripper capacity and productivity. The most recent series of Caterpillar dozers has a raised drive which improves output by keeping the drive mechanism clean.

The latest generation of hydraulic excavators (CAT 300 series and Komatsu PC 400's) are capable of excavating weak to moderately strong rock, often more effectively than the smaller rippers (i.e. D7 or D8's). However, it is stressed that this is very much dependant on the fracture state of the rock mass.

Where a rock mass cannot be excavated using digging or ripping methods then hydraulic breakers are usually introduced, particularly where localised difficult areas may be encountered. The use of hydraulic breakers has become increasingly popular especially where blasting may not be permitted or for confined trench excavation.

5.0 CASE HISTORIES

The authors' method of measuring and presenting core log fracture spacing data is now routinely carried out for ground investigations undertaken by IGSL. Two

case histories are described where the authors' graphic fracture spacing log has been analysed and used. The Intel Project deals with rock excavation, while Wexford Main Drainage relates to the prediction of block sizes for rock armour and rockfill.

5.1 Intel, Ireland, Fab 14 Structure, Leixlip, Co. Kildare

5.1.1 Background

Construction of a new wafer fabrication plant ('Fab 14') is currently being undertaken at Intel and involves some 115,000m³ of excavation. Approximately 65,000m³ of this involved excavation of argillaceous and calcisiltite limestones. The Fab 14 structure is 11,500m² in plan area and involves depths of excavation of up to 10.4m into the limestone bedrock. The site slopes gently from the N4 Dublin to Galway Road towards the River Rye. To date, the majority of the rock excavation has been completed and the excavated rock is being crushed and re-used for engineering fill.

5.1.2 Geology & Ground Conditions

Prior to construction, twelve NQ rotary core drillholes (54 diameter) were undertaken for the Fab 14 structure, these were extended to depths of between 7.0 and 14.0m below existing ground level, i.e. about 40.0m OD. Bedrock at the site comprises interbedded grey black argillaceous limestones and light grey calcisiltite limestones. Subordinate horizons of thinly laminated or fissile shales are associated with the

argillaceous units. These rocks are Lower Carboniferous (Holkerman to Brigantian) in age and are commonly referred to as "Calp".

The bedrock is folded with a wave length of about 40m. As is common for Caledonian folding, the fold axis has a northwest/southwest trend. The limestones are fine grained and bed thicknesses are up to 500mm in the calcisiltite units. The fracture spacings are generally less than 100mm in the argillaceous limestones. The shales / calcareous mudstones are predominantly moderately to highly weathered, very weak and non-intact.

The superficial deposits comprise over-consolidated stiff to locally very stiff brown and grey black gravely clays ('boulder clay

or lodgement till'). The thickness of these sub-soils varies from less than one to three metres. Occasional intra-glacial granular deposits were encountered during excavation. These proved to be dry and stable.

5.1.3 Fracture Data and Analysis

Blasting was ruled out due to the very close proximity and sensitivity of the existing Fab 10 plant to the excavation area. As a consequence, the method of assessing the excavability of the limestone bedrock became even more important. Detailed fracture logging was undertaken on each of the rock cores. The method of measuring the discontinuities was that previously outlined in Section 3.

Figure 13 Total Rock Mass Fracture Distribution

From the fracture data, a histogram of fracture spacing against cumulative percent of core was prepared. This is

shown in Figure 13. In terms of the overall percentages of each unit, 65% of the core pertains to the calcisiltite limestone with

the remaining belonging to the argillaceous unit. The calcisiltite units are dominant both in terms of strength and percentage of rock mass and were therefore expected to control the overall excavatability. For this reason, data on the

calcisiltite units was extracted from the data record sheets and a fracture spacing distribution analysis generated for this single lithology. This is presented in Figure 14.

Figure 14 Calcisiltite Units Fracture Spacing Distribution

This shows that approximately 37% of the calcisiltite units were expected to have fracture spacings of less than 100mm with 36% in the 100 to 200mm range. A summary of the percentages of the expected fracture spacings for the calcisiltite limestone is shown in Table 2.

Table 2 Expected Fracture Spacings – Calcisiltite Units

Percentage of Calcisiltite Units	Discontinuity Spacing (m)
37	<0.10
36	0.10 to 0.20
23	0.20 to 0.40
4	0.40 to 0.6

Point load strength (Is 50) data measured from the cores was then combined with the fracture spacing data and plotted on Pettifer & Fookes' excavatability chart. This is presented in Figure 15.

Figure 15 Pettifer & Fookes' Excavatibility Graph (1994)

Arg.LST. :- Argillaceous limestone 35% of total rock core

Cal.LST. :- Calcisiltite limestone 65% of total rock core

It can be seen from the afore-mentioned chart that the calcisiltite limestone mainly plots within the hard to very hard ripping category extending into the extremely hard ripping / hydraulic breaking zone. It is stressed that even within the calcisiltite units that the more competent rock was expected to control the overall method of excavation of the rock mass.

In contrast, the argillaceous limestones plot within the hard-digging / easy-ripping category.

5.1.4 As-Found Ground Conditions

Conventional bucket excavators (Cat 235's) were used to excavate the overburden soils and the highly fractured argillaceous limestone. Caterpillar D7, D8 and D9 rippers were then used to loosen the succeeding interbedded limestone

strata. These generally proved successful, but the more competent and strong calcisiltite limestone required hydraulic breaking ('Rockbreaker 1600 Rammers').

Overall the 'as-found' ground conditions correlated well with those predicted by the authors' fracture logging method and Pettifer & Fookes' excavability chart.

5.2 WEXFORD MAIN DRAINAGE (CONTRACT NO. 3)

5.2.1 Background

This contract is currently being undertaken by Irishenco and involves the construction of a vertical berthing facility, river training walls, reclamation embankments and a breakwater. A summary of the sizes of engineering rockfill and rock armour required for the afore-mentioned structures is shown in Table 3.

Table 3 Sizes or Grading of Rock Fill

Rock Material	Approx. Sizes (m)
Rockfill, Type 1	0.10 to 0.70
Rockfill, Type 1A	0.10 to 0.15
Rockfill, Type 2	0.025 to 0.20
Filter Material	< 0.23 (gen)
Rock Armour	< 0.62

After completion of a desk study to evaluate potential indigenous material sources, geotechnical investigations were undertaken at selected sites within the vicinity of Wexford Town.

The geotechnical fieldwork mainly comprised rotary core drilling (to depths of up to 27m) and trial excavations into bedrock at selected sites. This was followed-up with a comprehensive programme of geomaterials testing on the rock cores and block samples from the trial excavations. A summary of the geomaterials tests undertaken, based on specified quality requirements included:

- Water absorption and relative density
- 10% Fines Value & AIV's
- Slake Durability
- Magnesium soundness tests
- Petrographic analysis (thin sections)

5.2.2 Engineering Geology

Bedrock in the majority of the investigated sites comprised metamorphosed sandstones with subordinate units of siltstone and mudstone. These are referred to as "meta-greywackes" and have undergone several phases of deformation (folding, faulting, brecciation etc). The remaining sites were located within granite bodies or Carboniferous limestone.

Upon completion of the preliminary geotechnical investigations one "greywacke" site was selected for further evaluation. Detailed engineering geological core log records incorporating the authors' graphic fracture log were prepared. The fracture spacing data analysis provided a quantitative measure of the likely fracture state of the rock mass. This data was then used to

calculate the expected block sizes. These predictions were then used to evaluate the feasibility of producing materials within the grading characteristics types shown in Table 3.

5.2.3 Block Size Analysis

A block size distribution analysis was carried out utilising the fracture spacing data from the core drillholes. A frequency analysis of the fracture spacings was undertaken and the fracture spacings were converted into volumes. In carrying out the transformation from fracture spacings to block size volume, two assumptions were made:

- the joint surfaces are approximately orthogonal
- the blocks generated are approximately cubic in shape.

These assumptions were deemed to be reasonably accurate on the basis of the block shapes generated from trial excavations. The cumulative percentage volume passing was calculated and the block size distribution generated is presented in Figure 16.

Figure 16 Predicted Block Sizes from Core Drillholes

5.2.4 Conclusions from Block Size Analysis

Analysis of the fracture spacing data indicated a block size distribution with approximately 10% of the rock mass expected to produce block sizes in excess of 0,004m³. It was concluded from the fracture spacing analysis that the smaller

size materials could be produced from the greywacke sites but that primary and secondary rock armour would have to be resourced elsewhere.

No development has as yet taken place at the selected site, thus the as-found rock

mass conditions cannot be compared to those predicted.

6.0 CONCLUSIONS

In addition to reviewing rock mass excavability methods a graphical method for measuring and presenting fracture spacing data has been developed. The authors feel that the understanding of fracture spacing and its implications in civil engineering can be significantly improved using this method. Some of the key points of this paper are:

1. Fracture spacing and rock material strength (measured from point load tests) are considered by the authors to be the two most important parameters governing the rippability / excavability of a rock mass.
2. The design engineer must ensure that as much data as possible is extracted from rock cores, outcrops and trial excavations to assist in the understanding of the geotechnical properties of a rock mass. This is particularly important for projects which encompass rock excavation.
3. It is emphasised that the limitations associated with mechanical indices are fully appreciated, particularly RQD's which alone should not be used to determine the degree of intactness of a rock mass or its excavability characteristics.
4. Given the expenditure involved in undertaking rotary core drilling, careful measurements and interpretations of

the strength and discontinuities should be carried out by an experienced engineering geologist or geotechnical engineer to allow a full understanding of the degree of intactness and mechanical behaviour of a rock mass.

5. It is the opinion of the authors that a graphic fracture log should be specified and incorporated as part of a geotechnical core log record. This affords the opportunity to work with "real" fracture spacing data as opposed to mechanical indices. However, it would be unwise not to present the standard mechanical indices with which many people are familiar and from which several empirical correlations have been derived.
6. Once the fracture data is obtained, careful analysis is required to assess the characteristic fracture spacings associated with systematic joint sets. This analysis should consider the effects of orientation between drilling direction and systematic joint sets which may generate artificial distributions.
7. The authors' opinion is that Pettifer & Fookes' method is the most practical and easily applicable in the assessment of rock mass excavability. The authors' graphic fracture log and data analysis can now be used in conjunction with this to

categorise the required methods of

excavation.

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